

Novel α -mangostin derivatives as promising candidates against triple-negative breast cancer: in silico

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Abstract

Benzoyleated α -mangostin derivatives demonstrated improved pharmacokinetic and toxicity profiles compared to the parent compound and doxorubicin. In silico screening identified AM-4-Nitrobenzoate, AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate, AM-4-Aminobenzoate, and AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate as top candidates with lower binding energies and favorable interactions with key GSK3 β residues. Molecular dynamics simulations confirmed stable complex formation, with RMSD values below 3.5 Å and reduced RMSF fluctuations at the catalytic pocket. MM-PBSA analysis highlighted AM-4-Nitrobenzoate as the most potent binder (ΔG_{total} -18.87 kcal/mol), followed by AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate, AM-4-Aminobenzoate, and AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate, while α -mangostin and doxorubicin showed less favorable energies. Structural snapshots reinforced the persistence of ligand orientation and interactions, particularly for para-substituted derivatives. Overall, the integration of docking, MD simulation, and binding free energy analysis underscores para-substituted α -mangostin derivatives, especially AM-4-Nitrobenzoate, as promising scaffolds for GSK3 β inhibition in the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway relevant to triple-negative breast cancer.

Keywords

α -mangostin derivatives, GSK3 β inhibition, molecular docking, molecular dynamics simulation, triple-negative breast cancer

Introduction

According to data from GLOBOCAN in 2022, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) stated that breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed cancer type among women and the leading cause of cancer-related

mortality worldwide. In Indonesia, breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer, with 66,271 new cases reported, accounting for 16.2% of all cancer diagnoses. Overall, the country recorded over 408,661 new cancer cases (Bray et al. 2024).

Based on gene expression profiling, breast cancer can be classified into several subtypes, one of which is tri-

ple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) (Maqbool et al. 2022). Triple-negative breast cancer is characterized by the absence of estrogen receptors (ER), progesterone receptors (PR), and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2), occurring in approximately 15–20% of breast cancer cases. Triple-negative breast cancer contributes disproportionately to breast cancer mortality despite its relatively lower incidence compared with other subtypes (Yin et al. 2020). Triple-negative breast cancers are known for their aggressive nature, high heterogeneity, poor prognosis, and elevated risk of metastasis (Vagia et al. 2020). Currently, chemotherapy remains the primary treatment for triple-negative breast cancer, although it is associated with significant limitations, including drug resistance, severe side effects, and nonselective toxicity that can damage normal cells (Obidiro et al. 2023). Studies have shown that the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway is frequently upregulated in triple-negative breast cancer (Sakach et al. 2021). Therefore, understanding the molecular mechanisms underlying TNBC pathogenesis is essential for developing more effective and targeted therapies (Liao et al. 2021). Research indicates that β -catenin is crucial for tumorigenic behavior in triple-negative breast cancer cells both *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Zhang et al. 2020), suggesting that the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway could serve as a promising target for triple-negative breast cancer treatment.

In recent years, the compound α -mangostin (AM), which is obtained from the mangosteen fruit, has been extensively studied for its pharmacological properties both *in vitro* and *in vivo*, including its anti-breast cancer activity (Mardianingrum et al. 2025). Research by Kurose et al. (2012) demonstrates that α -mangostin extracted from the mangosteen rind induces apoptosis and affects the cell cycle in MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells (cell lines characterized by mutations in the p53 gene and negative expression of HER2, ER, and PR) through the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway. A further study investigated the potential of the α -mangostin structure to modulate the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway. In another study, Dewi and co-workers (2023) suggested that α -mangostin may exert its effect by targeting GSK3 β and CK1 α , which are key components of the β -catenin destruction complex (Dewi

et al. 2023). In addition, GSK3 β and CK1 α are mediators in the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway, particularly within the β -catenin destruction complex, where they regulate the phosphorylation of β -catenin. This process is modulated through interaction with the low-density lipoprotein receptor-related protein (LRP5/6), which introduces a regulatory mechanism that can suppress GSK3 β activity, thereby contributing to the stabilization of β -catenin in the cytoplasm (Lybrand et al. 2019).

Previous research has shown that the addition of $-\text{NH}_2$ and $-\text{CF}_3$ groups to pyrazole compounds, resulting in the compound N-(3-((4-amino-1-(trans-4-hydroxycyclohexyl)-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidin-3-yl)ethyl)phenyl)-4-methyl-3-(trifluoromethyl)benzamide, can enhance compound efficacy by improving absorption, pharmacokinetic properties, and targeting the apoptotic pathway in TNBC cells (Zhang et al. 2016). From this description, it is necessary to further develop the benzoylated α -mangostin (AM) derivative compound that was successfully synthesized (Mardianingrum et al. 2022) by modifying the benzoyl derivative in the form of $-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{NH}_2$, and $-\text{CF}_3$ groups on the aromatic ring. However, there are no benzoylated α -mangostin derivative compounds ($-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{NH}_2$, and $-\text{CF}_3$ on the aromatic ring) that have been tested against triple-negative breast cancer cells through the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway using *in silico*, *in vitro*, and *in vivo* approaches. Therefore, this study aims to identify compounds that have the potential to be active anti-cancer agents, particularly for triple-negative breast cancer.

Materials and methods

The *in silico* study involved ligand design

Thirteen ligand derivatives were designed by substituting the hydroxy group at the C6 position of the α -mangostin (AM) structure with benzoyl derivatives containing different functional groups ($-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{NH}_2$, and $-\text{CF}_3$) on the aromatic ring. The chemical structures were sketched using MarvinSketch (ChemAxon, Budapest) (Fig. 1; Table 1). Doxorubicin was used as the positive control.

Table 1. Modified α -mangostin (AM) with NO_2 , NH_2 , and CF_3 benzoyl chloride.

No	Compound	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	R ₆
1	AM-2-Nitrobenzoate	NO_2	H	H	H	H
2	AM-3-Nitrobenzoate	H	NO_2	H	H	H
3	AM-4-Nitrobenzoate	H	H	NO_2	H	H
4	AM-2,4-Dinitrobenzoate	NO_2	H	NO_2	H	H
5	AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate	H	NO_2	H	NO_2	H
6	AM-4-Dimethylaminobenzoate	H	H	$\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	H	H
7	AM-2-Aminobenzoate	NH_2	H	H	H	H
8	AM-3-Aminobenzoate	H	NH_2	H	H	H
9	AM-4-Aminobenzoate	H	H	NH_2	H	H
10	AM-2-Trifluoromethylbenzoate	CF_3	H	H	H	H
11	AM-3-Trifluoromethylbenzoate	H	CF_3	H	H	H
12	AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate	H	H	CF_3	H	H
13	AM-3,5-Bis-Trifluoromethylbenzoate	H	CF_3	H	CF_3	H

Figure 1. The structure of α -mangostin and the new compound α -mangostin derivatives.

The pharmacokinetic and toxicity profiles prediction

The absorption, distribution, and toxicity profiles of α -mangostin, native ligand (7YG), doxorubicin, and thirteen α -mangostin derivatives were predicted using the pKCSM server (<https://biosig.lab.uq.edu.au/pkcsm/prediction>). This server calculates the pharmacokinetic properties of drugs, which consist of human intestinal absorption (HIA), volume of distribution at steady state (VDss), blood–brain barrier (BBB) permeability, and Caco-2 permeability. The toxicity parameters were predicted *in silico* using the Ames test and oral acute toxicity (LD₅₀).

Receptor preparation

The crystal structure of human GSK3 β in complex with an inhibitor was downloaded from the Protein Data Bank database (PDB ID: 4ACC), with a resolution of 2.21 Å (Berg et al. 2012). The protein was further prepared using AutoDockTools 1.5.6. During the preparation, water molecules and the co-crystallized 7YG were removed, leaving only the protein structure. The validation of the docking protocol was performed by re-docking (control docking) 7YG into its original binding site to ensure the accuracy of the docking parameters.

Molecular docking

AutoDockTools 1.5.6 (The Scripps Research Institute, La Jolla) was used to prepare both the protein and ligands for the docking process. Polar hydrogens and Kollman charges were added to the protein, which was then saved in PDBQT format (Morris et al. 2009). Gasteiger charges

were assigned to the ligands. The grid box was set to a size of 50 × 50 × 50 points, centered at coordinates 18.393, 18.191, and 10.218 (x, y, and z Cartesian coordinates), with a spacing of 0.375 Å. The genetic algorithm was configured to run 100 iterations, while all other parameters were kept at their default settings. The docking simulations were performed using AutoDock 4.2.6, and the resulting binding affinities and interactions of the compounds were analyzed using Discovery Studio Visualizer v17.2.0.1634 (BIOVIA, San Diego).

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed on α -mangostin (AM) and its modified derivatives with NO₂, NH₂, and CF₃, as well as doxorubicin (positive control) and the N-ethyl analog BI-4481, which can be used as a negative control (Palomo et al. 2017), showing the lowest binding energy in the molecular docking. The MD simulations were carried out using the AMBER ff14SB force field for the protein, while the ligands were parameterized using the general AMBER force field (GAFF). The system was solvated with TIP3P water molecules in a 10 × 10 × 10 Å cubic box (Chakravorty et al. 2012). Topology files were generated after neutralizing ligand charges using the Restrainted Electrostatic Potential (RESP) method. The energy minimization, heating, and equilibration steps were performed using the Sander module in Amber 21. Before entering the production stage of the MD simulations, a step-wise heating protocol was applied to gradually increase the system temperature from 0 to 310 K in three stages, mimicking physiological conditions. This was followed by an equilibration phase to stabilize the system and ensure consistent energy and temperature levels. After equilibration,

production MD simulations were carried out. To evaluate the stability and flexibility of the ligand–receptor complexes, root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) and root-mean-square fluctuation (RMSF) analyses were performed. Both molecular docking and dynamics simulations were executed on a high-performance computing system equipped with an Intel VR Xeon CPU E5-2620 2.40 GHz and NVIDIA VR GeForce GTX TITAN X SSE2.

Results and discussion

In addressing the significant therapeutic challenges of triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC), an aggressive subtype of breast cancer that does not respond to hormonal or anti-HER2 therapies and is frequently associated with poor prognosis, the development of novel small molecules with optimized pharmacokinetic profiles and minimal toxicity has become a central focus of current research (Masci et al. 2023). Thirteen benzoylated AM derivatives exhibited superior pharmacokinetic properties compared with doxorubicin, which served as the positive control for TNBC treatment, as well as with AM, the parent compound. The pharmacokinetic data are presented in Table 2.

Based on the screening data presented in Table 2, the trifluoromethylbenzoate derivatives – particularly AM-3,5-trifluoromethylbenzoate – showed excellent oral intestinal absorption (HIA 100%), adequate Caco-2 permeability, non-mutagenicity (negative Ames result), and low acute toxicity. These parameters indicate its potential as a promising candidate for further development. Moreover, AM-4-Nitrobenzoate also displayed a favorable profile, characterized by high HIA, non-mutagenicity, and moderate LD₅₀ values, thereby reinforcing its potential as a safe and effective therapeutic candidate.

In comparison, AM, the lead compound, exhibits good permeability and absorption; however, its relatively low LD₅₀ of 1.89 mol/kg suggests high mutagenic potential, indicating the need for further structural optimization before clinical application. Meanwhile, doxorubicin, the standard chemotherapeutic agent for TNBC, demonstrates extensive tissue distribution and yields a positive Ames result (mutagenic), despite exhibiting relatively low acute toxicity. These findings align with clinical practice, where doxorubicin remains effective but is associated with severe side effects and a well-documented long-term toxicity profile (López-Camacho et al. 2022). In addition to the lead compound and doxorubicin, this study also included the negative control N-ethyl analog BI-4481, which has previously been recommended for *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluations due to its relatively safe biological profile based on screening results. Overall, these screening outcomes support that structural modification of α -mangostin, particularly with amino and trifluoromethyl substituents, successfully improves pharmacokinetic properties and safety, thereby yielding more promising candidates for the development of oral anticancer drugs.

Of the 13 AM derivatives, only ten compounds passed the pharmacokinetic and toxicity screening and were subsequently advanced to the *in silico* stage. In the *in silico* study, the initial step involved receptor validation (redocking). Receptor 4ACC was selected because it contains the human crystal structure of GSK3 β in complex with an inhibitor, with a binding energy of -7.99 kcal/mol and an RMSD value of 1.903 Å (Ruswanto et al. 2022). Key hydrogen bond interactions were observed with Asp133, Pro136, Arg141, and Asn186. The results of the receptor validation are presented in Fig. 2.

The docking process involved binding the ligands to receptor 4ACC, which comprises 465 amino acid residues,

Table 2. Pharmacokinetic and toxicity screening of AM, doxorubicin, BI-4481, and AM derivatives.

No	Compound	CaCO-2 (10^{-5} cm/s)	HIA (%)	VDss (log L/kg)	BBB (log BB)	AMES test (Yes/No)	Oral acute toxicity (LD ₅₀) (mol/kg)
1	Alpha-Mangostin (AM)	1.45	87.65	0.15	-1.11	Yes	1.89
2	Doxorubicin	0.19	68	1.44	-1.54	Yes	3.49
3	BI-4481	1.04	97.36	1.29	-0.21	No	2.85
4	AM-2-Nitrobenzoate	-0.24	98	-1.57	-0.79	Yes	2.67
5	AM-3-Nitrobenzoate	1.08	100	-0.96	-0.69	No	1.82
6	AM-4-Nitrobenzoate	-0.14	95.44	-1.44	-0.79	No	2.32
7	AM-2,4-Dinitrobenzoate	-0.37	94.65	-1.84	-1.27	Yes	2.39
8	AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate	-0.29	92.40	-1.78	-1.27	No	2.38
9	AM-4-Dimethylamino benzoate	1.48	96.83	0.16	0.32	Yes	1.85
10	AM-2-Aminobenzoate	0.88	96.58	-1.11	-1.32	No	2.34
11	AM-3-Aminobenzoate	1.01	91.44	-0.98	-1.31	No	2.37
12	AM-4-Aminobenzoate	0.99	91.47	-0.97	-1.33	No	2.39
13	AM-2-Trifluoromethylbenzoate	0.96	100	-1.02	-0.69	No	1.79
14	AM-3-Trifluoromethylbenzoate	1.08	100	-0.96	-0.69	No	1.82
15	AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate	1.02	100	-0.96	-0.71	No	1.82
16	AM-3,5- Bis-Trifluoromethylbenzoate	1.00	100	-0.83	-1.07	No	1.86

Note: color red: decline; black: approved.

Figure 2. Redocking receptor 4ACC (a) and visualization receptor 4ACC 2D (b).

using the same grid box parameters as in the redocking validation phase. The docking analysis focused on selecting the conformation of each compound with the lowest ΔG and inhibition constant (K_i) values (Gopinath and Kathiravan 2021). The docking results for doxorubicin, AM, and the ten AM derivatives are presented in Table 3.

Based on the molecular docking results for the ten AM derivatives, four compounds were identified as the most promising, as indicated by lower binding energies and hydrogen-bond interactions similar to those of doxorubicin and the native ligand. These compounds were AM-4-Nitrobenzoate, AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate, AM-4-Aminobenzoate, and AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate. Among them, AM-4-Nitrobenzoate exhibited the lowest binding energy (-10.81 kcal/mol), suggesting the most stable interaction between the ligand and the receptor (Muchtaridi et al. 2019).

The amino acid residues identified in the docking study, Lys85, Asp133, Pro136, Arg141, and Asn186, are part of the active site of GSK3 β and play a crucial role in stabilizing hydrogen bonds between the ligand or inhibitor and the protein (Weeks et al. 2021). Lys85 functions as a stabilizer of the negative charge of the ATP phosphate group, Asp133 acts as the catalytic base in phosphate transfer, Pro136 contributes to local conformational stabilization (loop rigidity), Arg141 is involved in electrostatic interactions with charged ligands, and Asn186 participates in the formation of hydrogen bonds with the ligand (Garcia et al. 2021).

Meanwhile, BI-4481, used as a negative control, was observed to interact with the same amino acid residues, Arg141 and Asp133. However, these interactions do not necessarily reflect comparable biological activity. This observation highlights the fundamental distinction between *in silico* and *in vitro* approaches, in which molecular docking and simulation analyses focus on interactions at the target amino acid level, whereas *in vitro* assays evaluate the overall cellular response, particularly in TNBC cells. Importantly, BI-4481 remains a valid negative control due to its weak binding affinity, unfavorable docking energy,

and the previously reported absence of significant anti-cancer activity in biological assays, thereby supporting its use as a reference compound for distinguishing true target-specific effects (Gollner et al. 2023).

Molecular dynamics simulation

The molecular dynamics simulation data over 100 ns were evaluated based on the mean values of root mean square deviation (RMSD), root mean square fluctuation (RMSF), and the total binding energy determined using the molecular mechanics–Poisson–Boltzmann surface area (MM-PBSA) approach. RMSD data can be seen in Table 4 and Fig. 3.

The root mean square deviation (Fig. 3) profiles over 100 ns revealed that all ligand–GSK3 β complexes remained stable throughout the simulation. The AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate–GSK3 β complex demonstrated an average RMSD (1.56 Å) that was nearly identical to the parent α -mangostin–GSK3 β complex (1.56 Å), while doxorubicin–GSK3 β exhibited a slightly higher mean deviation (1.67 Å). Substitution at the para (4-) position increased RMSD values moderately for AM-4-Nitrobenzoate (1.81 Å), AM-4-Aminobenzoate (1.99 Å), and AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate (2.11 Å), yet all remained within the range of dynamic stability (<3.5 Å), suggesting that no significant conformational drift occurred that would compromise ligand binding.

These data are consistent with prior simulations in which α -mangostin complexes with GSK3 β showed RMSD values between 1.5 and 2.0 Å over comparable trajectories (Dewi et al. 2022). Similarly, optimized pyrazolopyrimidine derivatives reported by Zhang et al. (2016) maintained stable binding with GSK3 β with an average RMSD <2.5 Å. Collectively, these results strengthen the view that para-substituted α -mangostin derivatives, particularly AM-4-Nitrobenzoate, preserve global stability comparable to or exceeding that of the parent compound and doxorubicin.

Table 3. Molecular docking results of AM, doxorubicin, BI-4481, and AM derivatives.

No	Compound	Binding Energy (kcal/mol)	Ki (μ M)	Hydrogen bond	Hydrophobic bond
1	Alpha-Mangostin (AM)	-9.34	0.14	Lys85 Glu97 Val135	Leu188 Val77 Phe67 Cys199 Val70 Ala83 Phe201
2	Doxorubicin (control positive)	-7.72	2.19	Lys85 Asp200 Asp133 Val135 Pro136 Gln185	Cys199 Val70 Phe67 Lys183 Ile62
3	N-Ethyl analog BI-4481 (control negative)	-8.04	1.28	Arg141 Asp133 Pro136	Ala83 Cys199 Glu137 Ile62 Leu188
4	AM-3-Nitrobenzoate	-9.77	0.07	Ile62 Phe201	Cys199 Val110 Asp200 Leu132 Lys85 Glu97 Val70 Leu188
5	AM-4-Nitrobenzoate	-10.81	0.01	Lys 85 Arg144	Tyr134 Ile62 Phe201 Val110 Leu132 Met101 Cys199 Val70 Arg141 Tyr140
6	AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate	-10.17	0.04	Lys85 Arg141 Arg144 Gln185 Tyr140	Ile62 Tyr134 Phe201 Val110 Leu132 Met101
7	AM-2-Aminobenzoate	-8.78	0.37	Val135 Lys183	Phe67 Leu132 Val110 Ala83 Cys199 Ile62 Leu188
8	AM-3-Aminobenzoate	-9.93	0.05	Tyr134 Pro136 Val135 Lys85	Thr138 Asp133 Cys199 Glu137 Phe67 Ile62 Leu188

No	Compound	Binding Energy (kcal/mol)	Ki (μ M)	Hydrogen bond	Hydrophobic bond
					Val70 Val110 Leu132 Leu130 Phe201 Met101
9	AM-4 Aminobenzoate	-10.44	0.02	Lys85 Lys183 Ile62 Val135	Phe67 Leu130 Leu132 Met101 Phe201 Val110 Val70 Asp133 Cys199 Leu188 Tyr134
10	AM-2-Trifluoromethyl benzoate	-7.94	1.52	Cys199	Ile62 Leu188 Tyr134 Lys85 Val70 Leu132 Arg141
11	AM-3- Trifluoromethyl benzoate	-8.95	0.27	Lys85 Val135	Leu188 Asp133 Met101 Leu132 Phe201 Val110 Cys199 Val70 Phe67 Ile62
12	AM-4- Trifluoromethyl benzoate	-9.98	0.05	Lys85 Val135	Asp133 Cys199 Ile62 Tyr134 Leu188 Val70 Phe67 Phe201 Met101 Leu132 Val110
13	AM-3,5- Bis-Trifluoromethyl benzoate	-8.43	662.75	Cys199	Val70 Val61 Arg141 Ile62 Leu188 Ala83 Lys85 Phe201 Val110 Leu132 Met101

Note: color red: decline.

Figure 3. RMSD graph of each compound in complex with GSK3 β .

Table 4. RMSD values of AM, doxorubicin, BI-4481, and AM derivatives complexed with GSK3 β .

Complex	Minimum–maximum (Å)	Average (Å)
AM-GSK3 β	0–2.79	1.56
Doxorubicin-GSK3 β	0–2.37	1.67
BI-4481-GSK3 β	0–2.72	1.87
AM-4-Nitrobenzoate-GSK3 β	0–3.26	1.81
AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate-GSK3 β	0–2.85	1.56
AM-4-Aminobenzoate-GSK3 β	0–3.31	1.99
AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate-GSK3 β	0–3.82	2.11

Root mean square fluctuation (Fig. 4) analysis indicated comparable fluctuation patterns across complexes, with higher mobility observed in terminal and surface loops, while the catalytic pocket remained relatively rigid. Key residues previously highlighted in docking studies, Lys85, Asp133, Pro136, Arg141, and Asn186, retained low to moderate fluctuations, reflecting persistent hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions throughout the trajectory. This stabilization of the binding site residues aligns with the low RMSD values and corroborates the strong interactions observed in docking.

The MM-PBSA analysis was employed to quantitatively evaluate the binding free energies of α -mangostin (AM), its selected derivatives, doxorubicin, and the negative control BI-4481 toward the target protein associated with TNBC. The total binding free energy (ΔG_{total}) was calculated by combining gas-phase interaction energies (ΔG_{gas}) and solvation energies ($\Delta G_{\text{solvation}}$), providing an integrated assessment of ligand–target stability.

Among all tested compounds, AM-4-Nitrobenzoate exhibited the most favorable binding affinity, with the lowest ΔG_{total} value (-18.87 kcal/mol), indicating the strongest and most stable interaction with the target protein. This strong binding was primarily driven by highly favorable electrostatic (EEL) and van der Waals interactions, which outweighed the opposing polar solvation energy (EPB). These results suggest that the nitro substitution at the para position significantly enhances target recognition and binding stability at the molecular level.

Similarly, AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate ($\Delta G_{\text{total}} = -9.38$ kcal/mol) and AM-4-Aminobenzoate ($\Delta G_{\text{total}} = -7.90$ kcal/mol) demonstrated substantially improved binding affinities compared with the parent compound. The enhanced binding of these derivatives can be attributed to optimized nonpolar (ENPOLAR) and dispersion (EDISPER) contributions, highlighting the importance of hydrophobic and π - π interactions in stabilizing ligand–protein complexes relevant to anti-TNBC activity. In contrast, the parent compound α -mangostin ($\Delta G_{\text{total}} = 1.55$ kcal/mol) and doxorubicin ($\Delta G_{\text{total}} = 5.34$ kcal/mol) showed unfavorable or weak binding free energies, indicating less stable interactions under the simulated conditions. This finding suggests that, despite its established clinical efficacy, doxorubicin may not optimally engage the selected molecular target in the context of this TNBC-related pathway.

Importantly, BI-4481, which served as a negative control, exhibited a near-neutral ΔG_{total} value (0.03 kcal/mol), reflecting negligible binding stability. This result is consistent with its weak docking affinity and supports its suitability as a negative reference compound, reinforcing that strong MM-PBSA binding energies observed for AM derivatives are not incidental but structurally driven.

Figure 4. RMSF graph of each compound in complex with GSK3 β .

Overall, the MM-PBSA results strongly support that structural modification of α -mangostin, particularly with nitro, amino, and trifluoromethyl substituents, significantly enhances binding stability and predicted target engagement relevant to TNBC. These findings provide *in silico* evidence that the optimized AM derivatives, especially AM-4-Nitrobenzoate, are promising candidates for further investigation as potential oral anti-TNBC agents (Zhang et al. 2016; Dewi et al. 2023).

These MM-PBSA rankings are highly consistent with docking predictions, in which AM-4-Nitrobenzoate displayed the lowest binding energy and a dense hydrogen bonding network with catalytic residues such as Lys85, Arg141, and Arg144. Similarly, AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate and AM-4-Aminobenzoate retained strong binding interactions. This concordance across docking, MD stability, and free energy analyses underscores that para substitution on the benzoyl moiety, particularly with electron-withdrawing groups such as $-\text{NO}_2$ or $-\text{CF}_3$, enhances the binding profile of α -mangostin derivatives.

In summary, the integration of RMSD, RMSF, and MM-PBSA data demonstrates that α -mangostin benzoyl derivatives, particularly AM-4-Nitrobenzoate, exhibit stable conformations, low local fluctuations at the active site, and the most favorable binding free energies toward GSK3 β . These findings highlight the promise of para-substituted α -mangostin scaffolds as potential inhibitors targeting the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway in triple-negative breast cancer.

To complement the numerical analyses of RMSD, RMSF, and MM-PBSA, molecular dynamics (MD) snapshots were extracted at different time points across the

100 ns trajectory (Table 6). These visualizations provide structural confirmation of the stability and persistence of ligand–protein interactions within the GSK3 β binding pocket. Snapshots enable direct inspection of conformational changes, ligand orientation, and the retention of critical hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic contacts that were predicted in docking and confirmed by dynamic analysis.

Across all systems, the snapshots reveal that the lead α -mangostin derivatives (AM-4-Nitrobenzoate, AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate, and AM-4-Aminobenzoate) consistently maintained a stable orientation within the catalytic cleft of GSK3 β . This observation corroborates the low RMSD fluctuations reported earlier, as well as the favorable binding free energies obtained by MM-PBSA. Notably, AM-4-Nitrobenzoate displayed minimal reorientation over time, with its para-substituted nitro group maintaining close proximity to polar residues such as Lys85 and Arg141, which are known to contribute to catalytic regulation of GSK3 β (Dewi et al. 2023).

In contrast, doxorubicin demonstrated more pronounced positional drift, as evidenced by moderate reorientation during later frames (snapshots 25–100 ns). This finding is consistent with its less favorable ΔG_{total} value (+5.34 kcal/mol) and supports the interpretation that doxorubicin, while clinically effective, is not inherently optimized for stable binding to GSK3 β (Zhang et al. 2016). Similarly, the parent α -mangostin maintained partial stability but exhibited less consistent orientation compared with its benzoylated derivatives, highlighting the structural advantage conferred by para substitution with $-\text{NO}_2$ and $-\text{CF}_3$ groups.

Table 5. The binding energies from MM-PBSA for AM, doxorubicin, BI-4481, and AM derivatives with GSK3 β from the 100 ns MD simulation trajectory.

Parameters (kcal/mol)	AM	Doxorubicin	BI-4481	AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate	AM-4-Aminobenzoate	AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate	AM-4-Nitrobenzoate
Van der Waals	-29.9493	-43.631	-21.6890	-45.7441	-25.7525	-44.223	-60.8227
EEL	-302.4119	-165.4065	-143.8351	-312.2304	-339.3438	-289.6068	-356.1135
EPB	314.3668	186.4568	155.250	324.6052	341.8491	297.5441	367.8819
ENPOLAR	-22.8506	-31.1959	-20.4416	-34.3709	-19.746	-36.5293	-45.4078
EDISPER	42.3938	59.1196	36.7453	61.4048	35.0957	63.4351	75.592
DELTA G GAS	-332.3612	-209.0375	171.5421	-357.9745	-365.0964	-333.8298	-416.9362
DELTA G SOLVATION	333.92	214.3805	171.5578	351.6391	357.1987	324.4499	398.0661
DELTA TOTAL	1.5488	5.343	0.0337	-6.3354	-7.8976	-9.38	-18.8701

Table 6. The snapshots of molecular dynamics simulations of the compound in GSK3 β .

No	Compound	2D visualization	Snapshots docking-MD overlay	Snapshots at 25-100 ns	Snapshot total
1	AM				
2	Doxorubicin				
3	AM-4-Nitrobenzoate				

No	Compound	2D visualization	Snapshots docking–MD overlay	Snapshots at 25–100 ns	Snapshot total
5	AM-4-Aminobenzoate				
6	AM-4-Trifluoromethyl benzoate				

The use of Docking-MD overlays in Table 6 further underscores the reliability of the docking predictions: compounds identified as top binders (e.g., AM-4-Nitrobenzoate) retained nearly identical orientations between the docking pose and their equilibrated MD frames, indicating strong convergence between static docking predictions and dynamic simulation results. This structural consistency reinforces the robustness of the computational pipeline used in this study.

Taken together, the snapshot analyses provide visual evidence that supports the quantitative findings from RMSD, RMSF, and MM-PBSA. The congruence between predicted docking poses and stable MD configurations strengthens the conclusion that para-substituted α -mangostin derivatives, especially AM-4-Nitrobenzoate, are highly promising scaffolds for the development of GSK3 β inhibitors targeting the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway in triple-negative breast cancer.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that benzoylated α -mangostin derivatives exhibit superior pharmacokinetic and safety profiles compared with the parent compound and the standard chemotherapeutic agent doxorubicin. Among the synthesized and computationally evaluated derivatives, AM-4-Nitrobenzoate emerged as the most promising candidate, supported by consistently stable RMSD and RMSF values, highly favorable binding free energy ($\Delta G_{\text{total}} -18.87$ kcal/mol), and persistence of interactions with key GSK3 β catalytic residues. Other derivatives, including AM-4-Trifluoromethylbenzoate, AM-4-Aminobenzoate, and AM-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate, also showed potential as effective inhibitors.

The integration of docking, molecular dynamics simulations, and MM-PBSA analyses strongly sup-

ports the para-substitution strategy ($-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{CF}_3$, and $-\text{NH}_2$) as a rational approach to optimize α -mangostin scaffolds for targeting GSK3 β within the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway. These findings highlight the relevance of structural modification in enhancing both stability and binding affinity, offering new directions for the development of selective therapeutics against triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC).

The results not only provide computational evidence but also align with preliminary synthesis and characterization of selected derivatives, bridging the gap between *in silico* prediction and experimental validation. Future studies involving *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays are warranted to confirm the biological efficacy and therapeutic potential of these derivatives.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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